

Regenerative Sanitation the Sixteenth Principle of Green Urbanism

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Abstract: Sanitation is regenerative when it integrates psycho-social, ecosystem, resource recovery and technological elements based on well-defined infrastructure standard specifications for the rejuvenation and revitalization of sanitation solutions in urban environments in a manner that mimics and contributes to contextual natural systems. This paper presents principles and proposed regenerative sanitation (ReGenSan) as the 16th strategic principle of green urbanism. This conceptual framework presents a systematic manner to tackle urban sanitation from holistic and integrated multi and transdisciplinary perspectives. It operates from an ecological-systemic worldview that embraces the dynamic complexities and unique peculiarities of 'place and scale'. The principles and framework were developed using mixed methods, content analysis, experiential knowledge and field practice. It identifies three interconnected subsystems (social-ecological, resource and technology), their eight dimensions and thirty-five components so as to foster innovative and practical solutions, especially in resource-constrained areas. ReGenSan could improve technology solutions across the sanitation service and value chain as well as ensure effective management of sanitation within sani-sheds for significant cost-saving and benefit-sharing whereby final waste transportation is minimally reduced. The framework is broad and flexible enough to integrate with the concept and perspectives of green urbanism, as it provides functional and progressive approaches towards supporting urban food security, greening and zero waste/emissions, maintaining environmental quality as well as improving and expanding access to sanitation services at a 'scale'. It could really provide the much-needed improvement and mind-change in sanitation system-thinking, research, management, planning and technology innovations in urban regeneration without compromising ecosystem sustainability.

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1. Introduction

Current urban sanitation practice evolved from the industrial revolution that mimicked the linear economic model of production and consumption to develop the conventional sanitation technological solutions (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2012/2013). The efficiency and effectiveness of these resource-intensive traditional sanitation systems of 'flush and discharge' or 'drop and store' generated sustainability concerns as there still remains a wide margin between desired results and reality (Esrey 2001, Fam and Mitchell 2012, Lopes et al. 2012, Andersson et al. 2016). In addition, urban sanitation facilities in developing countries are characterized with unimproved services with limited access to 'safely managed' infrastructure. Most of them are improperly operated and maintained and this causes extremely high abandonment rates of up to 42% due to failure and a lack of standard facilities for adequate faecal sludge management; and this comes with the attendant impact on public health and environmental quality (CSIR 2007, Rodgers et al. 2007, WSP 2007, Cookey 2013, Kaminsky and Javernick 2015, Cookey et al. 2016). Meanwhile, in developed countries, urban sanitation is challenged with aging sewer infrastructure that date back to over 100 years (19th century) when brick sewers were common, and now performance deterioration due to blockages, and leakages often resulting in infiltration and exfiltration results in poor service delivery (Brown and Caldwell 1984, USEPA 1991, Kemp 2000, Reynolds and Barrett 2003, Fenner and Saward 2004, Ashley and Hopkison 2002, Qasem et al. 2009, Corcoran et al. 2010, El-Sheikh 2011, Diagne 2013, Ahmadi et al. 2015, Miszta-Kruk 2016, Andersson et al. 2016). It is estimated globally that 1.5 billion sewer facilities operating in the world's urban centres are without adequate treatment and produce effluents of questionable standards (Mara 2003, Baum et al. 2013). These conditions impact urban sanitation management negatively and is evident in major infrastructural deterioration, dysfunctionalities and failures, and these directly affect biological diversity of aquatic ecosystems and soil quality, thereby disrupting the fundamental integrity of life support systems upon which a wide range of sectors from urban development to food production and industry depend (Corcoran et al. 2010) (Figure 1). These results also negatively impact on urban regeneration as it concerns housing, public and private infrastructure, greenery and landscaping, and environmental quality (Piana 2010) as poor sanitation increase the disease burden and cost of rebuilding and rejuvenating cities.

Figure 1. Global trend urban sanitation facility types 2000-2015 (generated from online wash database - WHO/UNICEF JMP 2017)

Provision of sanitation services for the fast growing urban population, estimated to be 4 billion people and constitute about 54% of the world's population, is one of the world's most urgent challenges (Andersson et al. 2016). It is also estimated that more than 756 million urban dwellers lack access to 'safely managed' sanitation facilities (Galli et al. 2014, UNICEF/WHO 2015, van Welie and Romijn 2018), particularly due to misappropriating and situating urban sanitation management within the broader contexts of 'urban renewal', 'green urbanism' and/or 'urban regeneration'; even in research (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Global trend urban sanitation services level 2000-2015 (generated from online wash database - WHO/UNICEF JMP 2017)

This is probably because urban development and the built environment discourse about cities often focus more on the astonishingly dynamic infrastructural technical complexities and downplay the fact that it also includes people who engage in more toilet and hygiene-related activities than any other known human-biophysical activities in their lifetime and this process impacts life and society. Sanitation is often lost in urban water management and disguised freshwater, wastewater and stormwater, components of watershed management strategies geared towards achieving urban water sensitive designs. This, of course, does not necessarily treat the core sanitation requirements for sustainability of urban cities (Tucci et al. 2009, Lehmann 2010, Anastasiadis and Metaxas 2013, Czischke et al. 2015). There is also the fact that generally people do not like to talk about the unsavoury business of by-products of digestion (urine and faeces), even though it is an unavoidable activity, and so it is hidden away under other matters like wastewater and solid waste management while the real concerns overrun metropolitan centres. This unconscious (or maybe not) disregard impedes the aims of the sustainable development goals (SDGs) for urban sanitation that advocates for inclusive, safe and resilient cities, which re-enforces the notion of a resource-based paradigm that closes the nutrient loop rather than waste-based disposal system (UNDP 2016, Bai et al. 2016, Schmitt et al. 2017). The resource-based paradigm considers sanitation as a production factory that can provide high quality bioenergy resources, safe fertilizers, and soil improvement materials that enhance ecosystem sustainability through delivery of new greenery to urban environment, increase biodiversity, climate change mitigation and water recycling for urban agriculture (crop and animal) (Winker et

al. 2009, Zareba et al. 2016); all of which contribute to the overarching objectives of green urbanism (Beatley, 2012b, 2005, Lehmann 2010). To this effect, the concept of regenerative sanitation (ReGenSan) is a strong tool in the mechanisms of green urbanism and urban regeneration. It could provide solutions for sanitation management in urban renewal projects and also supply resources for greening cities, providing livelihood support and working with regenerative agriculture/aquaculture to enhance and sustain food production and security.

The main objectives of this paper, therefore, is to present ReGenSan as the 16th strategic principles of green urbanism because the overall goals of ReGenSan align with the Green Urbanism conceptual model for zero-emission and zero-waste urban designs (Lehmann 2010) as well as recycling/upcycling and renewable energy use (Beatley 2005, 2012a,b,c). Urban sanitation is regenerative when it integrates psycho-social, ecosystems, resource recovery and technological elements based on well-defined infrastructural standard specifications for the rejuvenation and revitalization of sanitation solutions in urban environments in a manner that mimics and contributes to contextual natural systems (Koottatep et al. 2019). Clearly, sanitation should be recognized as an independent issue that requires concerted attention, which cannot be properly and adequately handled under urban water management as merely recycling greywater for urban greenery is not enough to deliver the goals and targets of SDG no. 6, such as:

- I. *Service improvement and access expansion to 'safely managed' infrastructure that will deliver functional and performance currently inherent in the 'improved' urban sanitation infrastructures (sewered and non-sewered);*
- II. *Retrofit and upgrade unimproved, failed, dysfunctional and abandoned non-sewered sanitation infrastructure in developing countries and rehabilitate poorly performing aging sewer systems in developed countries;*
- III. *Redesign existing urban sanitation infrastructure to be more regenerative by adopting technologies and processes that are systemic, contextual, integrate eco-efficiency with ecological-based approaches, recover and reuse value-added resources, and mimic natural systems to deliver improved functional and safely managed systems within the urban sani-sheds; and*
- IV. *Support local physical and socio-economic, cultural, spatial and decision making structures of the 'place' to support the adoption of appropriate and best applicable technological solutions because the dissonance between users, service providers, institutions, ecosystems and infrastructure could hinder progress in urban sanitation pursuits.*

Even though the importance of sanitation in the sustainability of urban areas is acknowledged, it has often been overlooked in favour of other types of development by urban decision-makers, national government and users, most likely contributes to persistent unsustainable systems that do not guarantee proper containment and sanitization of excreta (Andersson et al. 2016). It is, therefore, essential to push forward in the direction of sanitation solutions that yield increased efficiency and effectiveness, reduced costs and risks, upgraded livelihoods and ecological sustainability as well as accelerated drive towards expanded access and improved services by 2030. This is crucial as sanitation could provide much-needed solutions for some current challenges facing cities while providing opportunities to ensure food, water and energy security (Andersson et al. 2016).

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Content analysis

An iterative mixed methods approach of 'input-processing-output-outcome' was adopted in developing this framework by combining technical, experimental and experiential practical knowledge as well as through literature review that included previous related theories, researches and concepts used to represent similar problems (Sethi and King 1998, Brewerton and Millward 2001, Mayring 2003, Levy and Ellis 2006, Seuring and Muller 2008, Novak and Canas 2008, Campbell et al. 2015, Martinez-Jurado and Moyano-Fuentes 2014, Bocken et al. 2014) (Figure 3). The holistic integrated system research approach from Pahl-Wostl et al. (2011) was also adopted together with evidences from scientific literature to assess ongoing discourse for a paradigm shift from techno-centric sanitation system to integrated holistic sanitation system. To assess the current state of development in this direction, a bibliometric analysis of publications was conducted using SCOPUS database, whereby different combinations of keywords were applied to define search terms. The resulting dataset shown in Table 3.1 records the number of publications in peer-reviewed journals in the search space (Pahl-Wostl et al. 2010).

Figure 3 Methodology to develop Regenerative Sanitation conceptual framework

2.2 Descriptive analysis

Researches on sanitation focus primarily on technology and the impact of sanitation on health, hygiene and water. Publications on sanitation-related science show serious emphasis on technology over integrated systems and governance, including the increase in publications with integrated systems and governance in recent years. In the case of integrated sanitation systems, the publications grew from 14 in 2002 to over 44 in 2015; while sanitation management and governance grew from 2 publications in 2002 to 15 in 2016. There was also an increase in researches that focused on resource recovery and reuse. The data showed that not much researches focused on retrofitting, rehabilitation and repairs of sanitation infrastructures, which indicate that sanitation is a missing link in the concepts of 'green urbanisms' and 'urban regeneration'. For instance, there were only 15 publications on sanitation and urban regeneration while there

was zero publication on sanitation and green urbanisms. This suggests the need for the integration of sanitation into the green urbanism and urban regeneration fields of study and practice. It implies then that there a place for the holistic, integrated and systemic ReGenSan conceptual framework, designed to address the core challenges of urban sanitation and embraces the dynamic complexities and contextual issues of location-specific urban cities while delivering context-dependent integrated solutions.

3.0 RESULTS

3.1 Regenerative sanitation principles

The study formulated and developed 10 principles conceived to guide planning, research and development of ReGenSan which could support the advancement of urban sanitation. Table 2 shows the summary of the 10 key principles of ReGenSan. The principles provide an opportunity for new ways to learn about urban sanitation, seek fresh answers from old ways, adapt to change with resilience and flexibility, think then act and work to integrate and synergize the whole process of urban sanitation management as a whole system (and not just working from individual parts). ReGenSan sees sanitation as resource, service and products development and management rather than problem management as sanitation has always being fingered as the culprit that pollutes water resources (but the blame should be placed squarely on inadequate management and failure to harness the resource potential inherent in the sanitation system. It aims to reduce the transfer of burden from urban sanitation management, provide sanitation-derived products and services, incorporate restoration/rehabilitation, and ensure continuous improvements. These principles are designed to work together as an integrated whole and not just parts – and it is only when they are imputed together that they give desired results.

Table 2 Summary of ReGenSan principles and interpretation

S/No	Regenerative sanitation principles	Summary Interpretation
1	Appropriate technology (ApT)	Technology that is appropriate for particular 'place' and 'scale'
2	Biomimicry and Biophilia (BaB)	Sanitation solutions/strategies that mimic and support natural systems
3	Fit-for-purpose governance (FPG)	Governance mechanisms that fit the place and scale and purpose for functional, efficient and effective sanitation requirement
4	Hybridized solutions (HS)	Sanitation solutions that could synergize centralized and decentralized options to deliver effective and efficient services to particular 'place' and 'scale'.
5	No-transfer-of-burden (NToB)	Sanitation solutions that do not transfer health, environment, social, economic and ecological burdens to society
6	Systemic holistic integration (SHI)	Sanitation solutions that interconnect and synergize subsystems, dimensions and components to achieve functional, efficient, and effective whole systems
7	Place and scale (PaS)	Sanitation solutions that indigenously align to location (place) and sites (scale) for optimization
8	Participation and partnership (PaP)	Sanitation solutions that involve stakeholders at all spheres and levels of localized contexts
9	Recycling and safe reuse (RaSR)	Sanitation solutions that recover and safely reuse valuable resources by-products of human digestion.
10	Rehabilitation of dysfunctional facilities (RoDF)	Sanitation solutions that rehabilitate and retrofit dysfunctional. Unimproved and aging infrastructure

The overall goal here is to refocus the perspectives of researchers, professionals, practitioners, advocacy-agents, policy makers and solution-providers from attacking a problem (of health, hygiene, and water quality) to providing services, products and solutions; and ultimately, expanding access as well as improving service towards achieving the SDG no. 6 by 2030.

3.2 The Regenerative sanitation conceptual framework

The ReGenSan framework is conceptualized from these stated 10 principles. The elements include sub-systems, dimensions, components and their relationships, attributes and interactions. ReGenSan fits the complex dynamic 'system of the systems' where subsystems (socio-ecological, technology and resource systems) are linked with each other (Figure 4/Table 3).

Figure 4: Integrated ReGenSan subsystems, dimensions, components and principles

The subsystems summarised below (for details see the upcoming book - 'Regenerative Sanitation:- A Framework for Sanitation 4.0' from the IWA Publishers (Koottatep et al. 2019).

- I. *Social-ecological system (SES): seeks to provide better understanding of the interactive effects of psychosocial, cultural, economic, geographical and ecological issues that influence the whole spectrum of sanitation science, governance, practice and technology guided by knowledge and skills within the SES, especially as it concerns contextual expectations for green urbanism and upgrading urban cities. It consists of two dimensions: psychosocio-ecophilia and governance and seven components;*
- II. *Technology system (TeS): is the configurations of infrastructures and services combined to treat by-products of human digestion from the point of generation to the final point of reuse and/or disposal. It includes an extensive range of possible combinations of technical and socio-technical components driven by sanitation infrastructural standardization to deliver the most appropriate and best applicable solutions for growing cities and their dense areas. TeS encompasses the entire sanitation service chain and its flow within urban environments. There are three dimensions to TeS {Existing Improved Design and Technology (EIDT), Restorative Design and Technology (RDT), and Nouveau Design and Technology (NDT)} and twelve components;*
- III. *Resource system (ReS): is concerned with 'closing the loop' by turning the linear resource management schemes of sanitation systems into a cyclical one and to support the sanitation economy that could eventually strengthen a city's circular economy. ReS focuses on how to recover and reuse valuable resources from sanitation systems within old and emerging cities that will help minimize depletion of natural resources and reduce environmental degradation, sustain livable cities with sustainable energy recovery/conservation, contextual innovative solutions for housing, land use, greening, recycling/upcycling, and regenerative/circular economy (Beatley 2015, 2012a,b,c, 2005, Fullerton, 2015, EMF 2017, 2015). Recovering and reusing the valuable resources present in excreta, urine and wastewater contribute to resource efficiency and improved food security. ReS has three dimensions {design for recovery and reuse (DeRaR), sanitation service chain raw materials (SSC-RaMs), and sanitation-derived products (SDPs)} and sixteen components.*

The ReGenSan framework is unique in that it is applicable to both developed and developing countries, and to all stages, processes and cycles for delivering sanitation solutions. It captures the essential characteristics of a 16th strategic principle of green urbanism as it contains some elements and structures announced by several authors in literature (Beatley 2012b,c, 2005, Lehman 2010a). This interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary framework contributes to an understanding of sanitation's complex-dynamic, systemic and integrated roles in urban regeneration/greening. It is based on an ecological worldview wrapped around 'place' and 'scale' focus where comprehensive sanitation solutions are provided within sani-sheds. ReGenSan's-sheds imply that sanitation systems should be tailored to the unique features of the 'place' by exploring the opportunities and solutions that are indigenously akin to the specific 'place' (location), 'scale' (site) and context. In other words, urban sanitation management should be committed to the sani-sheds by ensuring that issues such as wastewater, faecal sludge, resource recovery, etc., are contained and managed within their sphere of influence, thus reducing material transfer for treatment at other locations. Therefore, this framework aims to cause improvement and mind-change in sanitation planning, technology innovations and implementation. It provides a functional and progressive approach towards improving and expanding access to sanitation services at a 'scale' in cities by achieving net-benefits for all relevant actors (Potter et al. 2011, Kvarnström 2011). The framework combines and integrates sanitation processes and technologies into a systemic whole that addresses the interconnectedness of socio-cultural-economic, environmental, technical and institutional aspects of sanitation management (Marshall and Farahbakhsh 2013). The aim is to ensure that sanitation systems do not transfer ecological and public health burdens, but ensure overall gains to people and environment.

ReGenSan applies diagnostic (Ostrom 2005), prescriptive (Cookey et al. 2016b) and normative (Pahl-Wostl 2009) analytical approaches designed to deliver comprehensive, integrated and adaptive sanitation solutions (sani-solutions) with contextual and locational focus. There is the potential to critically evaluate, analyze and provide credible, adequate and appropriate sanitation solutions by adopting techniques that focus on core sanitation concerns within specific areas (Ostrom 2005, Pahl-Wostl 2009, Cookey et al. 2016a). The 'diagnostic' provides detailed existing status reports for interventions that are geared towards either restorative, existing or nouveau solutions. The 'prescriptive' is built upon the diagnostic and strategically determines the appropriateness and adequacy of the applied interventions and at the same time promotes continuous improvement of sanitation systems. The 'normative' is associated with the governance and PSEP considerations that provide optimum enabling and operating environment for uptake of scalable solutions. Together, they provide better comprehension of the interconnections of knowledge and interactions among the sanitation sub-systems, dimensions and components.

4.0 DISCUSSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

ReGenSan could fortify green urbanism and the overarching aspirations of urban regeneration as a 'place-based' localized, contextual and strategic intervention for improved access and delivery of safely managed sanitation in urban cities (Figure 5). It could also add to the benefits and impact of green urbanism, particularly in urban regeneration strategies for cities (new and old) as it provides reusable resource (i.e. energy, nutrients, fertilizer, fiber, manure, etc), entrepreneurial and employment opportunities, public health protection, sanitation (and related) infrastructural provision, appropriate technology and transportation route (i.e. reuse of sanitation resource, etc), land use planning (i.e. constructed wetlands, space for treatment and production of sanitation-derived-products, etc), protection of natural systems (air, soil, water), guidelines for design, construction, installation and fabrication of sanitation devices/facilities for specific places in cities, community interaction and government involvement among others. Specifically, ReGenSan supports the three aims of green urbanism and could contribute to some green urbanism principles: (i) renewable energy for zero CO₂ emissions; (ii) zero-waste city; (iii) landscape, gardens and urban biodiversity; (iv) local and sustainable materials with less embodied energy; (v) density and retrofitting of existing districts; (vi) green buildings and districts, using passive design principles; (vii) local food and short supply chain; (viii) urban governance, leadership and best practice; (ix) education, research and knowledge; and (x) strategies for cities in developing countries (Lehmann 2010a,b). Beatley's livable cities, land use and urban reforms, innovative housing strategies, sustainable transportation, urban ecology and greenery, recycling and upcycling, energy conservation and renewable energy, sustainable building practices, and sustainable economy/governance (Beatley 2015, 2012a,b, 2005) could feed and gain from ReGenSan.

Building livable cities around a circular economy that pursue after reduced waste, resource recycling, natural systems adaptation, biophilic designs and plans, alternative energy and emission controls (Beatley 2005, 2012a,b, 2015, 2010, Beatley and Newman 2013, Lehman 2010a,b,c) will require cost-effective ways to recover, transform and reuse sanitation resources.

Sub-systems	Dimensions	Cross-cutting components	Components
Social-ecological system (SES)	Psycho-socio-ecophilia (PSEPE): provides contextual and socio-technical contributions for decision-making in sanitation infrastructure and management solutions as well as provides the needed socio-ecological-technology fit.	(i) Continuous improvement+ (CM), (ii) knowledge and skills+ (Kas)	(i) <i>Psycho-social-cultural:</i> religion, norms, customs, availability, accessibility, acceptability, willingness to use, gender-equity, inclusiveness, perceptions and attitude, health, hygiene and handwashing, prevention, status. (ii) <i>Socio-economic:</i> educational level (formal and informal), income level (affordability, willingness-to-change and willingness-to-pay), livelihood support (economic activities and occupational engagement), access to basic services (water supply, electricity, and healthcare), access to sanitation services and types (sewer, on-sewer, shared and non-shared facilities), geographical location (urban and rural), housing/dwelling types, household sizes and head of household, age, gender and race
	Governance: -provides an enabling environment, standards and regulations, funding mechanism and asset management procedures with the socio-ecological support for the uptake of functional and adaptable technologies and resource recovery fit for the 'place' and 'scale'		(iii) <i>Bio-geo-chemical:</i> nutrients and water (C, N, P, H ₂ O) cycling, ecosystem services and functions, fauna and flora (iv) <i>Institutions:</i> policies, legislation and regulations, informal institutions, international treaties and protocols (v) <i>Management:</i> sanitation management entities (SMEs), planning and implementation, assets management, clearly defined roles of actors, stakeholders information and communication, regulatory compliance and enforcement, monitoring and evaluation (vi) <i>Sustainable financing:</i> Blending public and private funding sources, resource leverage, cost recovery and life cycle costing, supplementary income and social marketing, and utilization of local/domestic private sector (i) <i>service chain functionality and serviceability;</i> (ii) <i>integrity, reliability, safety, and quality;</i> (iii) <i>preventive and proactive maintenance;</i> (iv) <i>inspection and monitoring;</i> and (v) <i>infrastructure standardization*</i>
Technological system (TeS)	Existing improved design technology (EIDT): focuses on continuous service improvement, expansion of access and coverage of the currently adjudged improved and safely managed sewer and non-sewer sanitation facilities estimated to be used by 5 billion people		(vi) <i>Rehabilitation,</i> (vii) <i>retrofitting,</i> and (viii) <i>remediation and mitigation</i>
	Restorative design technology (RoddT): addresses the issues of upgrading and retrofitting of dysfunctional, aged, disused and unimproved, basic and limited sanitation facilities for both sewer and non-sewer to safely managed sanitation estimated to be used by 2.4 billion people		(ix) <i>Designs for service and products (DeSaP),</i> (x) <i>design for nature (DeN),</i> and (xi) <i>design for the base of the pyramid (DeBoP),</i>
Resource system (Res)	Nouveau design technology (NoDT): focus on the issues of emerging novel sanitation facilities solutions because of failure of current technologies to address the underlying challenges behind the lack of sanitation infrastructure and resources recovery as well as provide better alternative for new development area and the population exposed to open defecation estimated to be nearly 1 billion people		(i) <i>Recovery on reuse from existing facilities,</i> (ii) <i>alternative design for recovery and reuse,</i> (iii) <i>demand based design,</i> and (iv) <i>health and safety;</i> (v) <i>integrated functional sanitation value chain (IFSVC)*.</i>
	Design for recovery and reuse (DeRaR): provides technological and infrastructural support for operationalization of Res,		(v) <i>feces,</i> (vi) <i>urine,</i> (vii) <i>flushwater,</i> (ix) <i>greywater;</i> (x) <i>anal cleansing water and other materials,</i> and (xi) <i>sludge (faecal and sewage)</i>
	Sanitation service chain raw materials (SSC -RaMs): provides the input materials for Res		(xii) <i>used water,</i> (xiii) <i>sanitation-derived fertilizers(SDFs)</i> (xiv) <i>bioenergy;</i> (xv) <i>soil conditioners,</i> and (xvi) <i>other output materials, e.g. protein feed, building materials, trace element</i>
	Sanitation-derived products (SDPs): provides recoverable and reusable products sanitation systems		

* Components applicable to all dimensions of technology sub-system

+ Components applicable to all subsystems

Figure 5: Connection between ReGenSan and green urbanism cross cutting issues entering point's benefits from addressing urban sanitation regenerative

Otherwise, the laudable objectives may be constrained due to the unconscious disregard of core sanitation in planning and design (e.g. sewer blockages and leakages, blackwater and sludge overflow into surface and ground water, foul odours and ugly sight of exposed excreta, health costs and mortality, and the loss of revenue from sanitation-derived-products); just as it could also benefit from incorporating ReGenSan into its train of principles with the objectives to increase access to safely managed sanitation in the world's cities (to protect public health, environmental quality, reduce attendant costs, etc), improve sanitation service delivery (e.g. emptying, collection, storage, transportation, treatment/disposal), upgrade designs and development of sanitation devices and facilities (i.e. fabrication, construction, installation and connections of toilets, sewers, septic tanks, etc), provide organic resources for horticulture, urban greenery/landscapes, food (crop and animal) production, building materials and energy, support and protect natural systems, ensure sustainable governance and economy through instruments that engender the reuse of sanitation products and strengthen a sanitation economy within the city. It becomes expedient for urban planning and built environment professionals to work with sanitation professionals to embed core sanitation expectations towards inspiring effective and practical situations for the world's cities that do not negate the objectives of green urbanism and urban regeneration (as could be seen in cities of developing countries where streets are laden with sanitation matter and related disease burden is high). So, how does ReGenSan, as the 16th Green Urbanism principle contribute to the overall goal?

- I. Sanitation is key in urban planning as people will always actively perform the related physiological activities several times a day (imagine the population in the metropolitan areas across the world). Therefore, failing to plan for sanitation management from the initial stage or as a major objective may hinder progress or even ruin success.
- II. Sanitation resources contribute to cities as sanitation-derived-products will be used in home-gardens, green roofs and walls, city parks and other greeneries, flower and plant shops, farms (crop/animal), building construction, cooking, lighting homes and municipal administrative buildings, powering essential facilities (e.g. schools, health centres, community halls, etc), stadium fields, etc.
- III. Resource recovery and reuse through recycling/upcycling and product transformation will reduce the amount cities spend on disposal and thereby protect the environment, public health (by reducing human contact...less hospitalizations and expenses), ensure the aesthetics of the city, etc.
- IV. Energy recovery and reuse will provide renewable energy for use at varying degrees and result in energy conservation which could affect carbon emissions and climate change.
- V. With appropriate technology designs, cities can have sanitation systems that fit their urban development plans and unique peculiarities and contexts (coastal, arid, mountain, densely-populated, luxury, industrial, etc).
- VI. With systemic, holistic and integrating sanitation planning and management, cities can make the best use of land space, natural systems (e.g. wetlands, groundwater recharge, surface water nutrient for aquaculture, etc), transportation and conveyance routes for sanitation material, robust marketplace, etc.
- VII. The population at the base-of-the-pyramid (BoP) in developing countries, who mostly live in poorer dense areas, could be adequately planned for and the homeless as well.
- VIII. Failed, unimproved, dysfunctional and abandoned sanitation facilities can be retrofitted, rehabilitated, repaired and/or the space recovered for proper use while new facilities could be appropriately sited.
- IX. The integrated functional sanitation value chain could create entrepreneurs, enterprises, employees and business networks that support the sanitation economy that in turn feeds the city's overall economy.
- X. A structured focused governance system will provide the enabling environment that ensures sanitation management goals that aim not just for the SDG 6 targets, but also zero waste/emissions, energy recovery/reuse, food security, public/environmental quality and so on.
- XI. ReGenSan will provide architects, engineers, planners, policy-makers and city dwellers with fodder to determine the particular sanitation devices, facilities and infrastructural system required to benefit the overall city expectations and green urbanism designs.
- XII. Special financing mechanisms could support innovation and upscale of sanitation products and services as well as infrastructural developments within the city.

ReGenSan within the context of green urbanism refers to a range of socio-cultural, economic, ecological and technical strategic initiative design that ensure serviceability and functionality of the sanitation service chain (SSC) and implements a market-based integrated and functional sanitation value chain from design, production, marketing, delivery of products and services, especially for resource recovery and reuse (RRR) within city frameworks. The overall purpose is to ensure continuous improvement with existing improved urban sanitation infrastructure, retrofit dysfunctional facilities, and provide opportunities for emerging innovative infrastructural technological solutions that incorporate RRR within the context of urban environments' socio-ecological systems. Consequently, ReGenSan policies and processes within green urbanism programmes shall seek to address the following issues:

- I. *Ensure infrastructural standardizations, especially with non-sewered sanitation systems in urban cities of developing countries;*
- II. *Ensure that urban sanitation infrastructure delivers products and services, particularly in harnessing resources from the sanitation systems to support urban cities renewable energy, local food supply and value chain, and green landscapes;*
- III. *Design urban sanitation solutions to address cities population at the base-of-the-pyramid (BoP); and*
- IV. *Align urban sanitation infrastructure with urban landscape to support biodiversity by mimicking nature's modes, processes and ecosystem and adapting them to solve sanitation challenges.*

It is in this regard that we propose the inclusion of ReGenSan strategies into green urbanism the 16th principle to address core urban sanitation issues, which are missing in the current frame of green urbanism. This will breakdown the traditional limits that confine urban sanitation infrastructure and service provision to the water sector; barriers that also impact on how we think about and perceive systemic boundaries relating to urban sanitation and its impact on metropolitan regeneration.

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